

OPPORTUNITIES FOR PEDAGOGICAL COOPERATION IN ENSURING THE QUALITY OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION FOR CHILDREN WITH LIMITED HEALTH CAPABILITIES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10118820>

Abstract. *This work is aimed at studying ways of social support for children with disabilities in the activities of public organizations, which is of interest for research in social work.*

Keywords: *disabilities, inclusive education, rehabilitation, rehabilitation center, charity.*

Introduction.

It seems that the study of social support for children with disabilities in the activities of public organizations will in the future make it possible to form an adequate system of means to counter the situation when such children cannot sufficiently find their place in society. The situation in society that has developed in connection with the formation of public organizations and associations makes it possible to find appropriate ways to provide assistance to this socially vulnerable category of the population, timely support for young citizens of Russia who could forever find themselves in an extremely difficult life situation.

It is understood that the continuation of the coronavirus pandemic and the resulting self-isolation regime may continue to significantly contribute to the alienation of children who have certain limitations in terms of physical or mental health, as well as conditions in one way or another caused by special genetic predispositions. In turn, this circumstance can contribute to a significant increase in the number of people seeking help from public organizations and associations, whose activities are directly or indirectly aimed at comprehensive social support for children with disabilities.

Accordingly, this affects a much wider range of children with disabilities, whose needs for social support will require appropriate attention from employees of public organizations and associations.

However, this aspect of the work will also be of interest for the development of social work, so it seems necessary to us to touch upon this issue.

The problem at the heart of the study: further, increasingly in-depth research into the process of social support for children with disabilities in the activities of public organizations.

Purpose of the study: to study the process of social support for children with disabilities in the activities of public organizations.

Research objectives:

1. Analyze the socio-psychological characteristics of children with disabilities in physical and mental health.
2. Consider the socio-psychological characteristics of children with autism spectrum disorders.
3. Explore the features of the work of public organizations in providing social support to children with disabilities.
4. Present the practical results of the rehabilitation center's activities for the rehabilitation and habilitation of children with physical disabilities such as cerebral palsy, stroke, and injury.
5. To study the practical results of the activities of the rehabilitation center for the rehabilitation and habilitation of children with mental disorders such as mental retardation and mental retardation.
6. Consider the practical results of the activities of the rehabilitation center for the rehabilitation and habilitation of children with autism spectrum disorders

Object of study: Children with disabilities.

Subject of research: The process of social support for children with disabilities.

The degree of scientific development of the problem. For many years, this problem has been the focus of attention of such scientists as E. A. Bayer, S. P. Demura, V. N. Ilyin, V. A. Kovtonyuk, O. Yu. Latyshev, L. B. Levin, L.N. Makarova, V.S. Mukhina, E.V. Petrova, V.A. Podkopaeva, G.V. Semya and many others.

The practical significance of the work is that the practical results of the activities of the rehabilitation center for social support of children with disabilities can be used throughout the Russian Federation in various similar rehabilitation centers.

Research base: Rehabilitation center.

The research conducted in this work allows us to draw the following conclusions:

The socio-psychological characteristics and special educational needs of modern students with disabilities are very variable. And although in this work we have examined only some of the limitations of health in children, nevertheless, it becomes clear that it is media education in a rehabilitation center that in each case can have a significant impact on the formation of the personality of children with various developmental delays.

The ability of children with special educational needs to learn how a variety of media works, to restructure, supplement and combine them at their own discretion for any educational purpose gives them the opportunity to receive a multifaceted quality education and use it well throughout their lives. It seems to us that it is in relation to students with special educational needs that media education has an excellent chance of rapid and widespread development.

The socio-psychological characteristics of children with autism spectrum disorders are realized in conditions of direct support from the polysensory complex. It includes sensations of the conventionally designated sensory horizontal and vertical. The sensory horizon is served by physical sense organs that perceive information through movement (kinetics), touch (kinesthetics), vision (visual sensations), hearing (auditory sense), smell (odorant sense) and taste. The sense of sensory verticality is accompanied by hierarchical mechanisms of the cognitive process. These are intuitive sensations that stimulate emotional-volitional manifestations with corresponding sensors, previously designated as somotor feelings, symbolic sensations, logical and speech sensory.

Therefore, it seems to us that for children with autism spectrum disorders, our rehabilitation center can organize proactive support that fully takes into account all their socio-psychological characteristics.

The team of each newly created rehabilitation center or center for psychological and pedagogical rehabilitation and correction must carefully approach the problems that exist within their specific region of the country. At the same time, the team must obtain a complete understanding of the range of tasks that this particular institution will have to solve.

The nature of the work of each specific rehabilitation center will be very different from the nature of the work of similar institutions in other regions. Accordingly, it is necessary to very clearly and fundamentally motivate the top management to equip the institution with certain special devices and areas that imply the process of social support for children with disabilities in rehabilitation, correctional and educational activities of one nature or another.

Accordingly, the staffing schedule for each specific rehabilitation center will be built. The recruitment of specialists from different centers, despite the commonality of their names, may differ radically in accordance with the quality of the tasks being solved. Secondly, the difference between one similar institution and another will be followed by a difference in the quality of the content of the zones where certain educational practices will be implemented for a certain contingent of children. And finally, thirdly, the system of devices designed to meet the physical needs of one or another category of children should also clearly vary depending on the occupancy of the institution with one or another contingent.

In matters of rehabilitation of children with certain deviations in physical and mental development, they are not left alone with their problems, but always find protection in rehabilitation centers, scientific, cultural and educational institutions, which together help such children to believe in the future.

The practical results of the rehabilitation center's activities for the rehabilitation and habilitation of children with mental disorders such as delayed mental or speech development are quite wide, abundant and varied.

Of course, this does not mean that at the moment the final result of this work has been achieved, which would allow the identification of certain qualitative and quantitative statistical data that are recognized as sufficient.

However, even now, the staff of the rehabilitation center expresses a feeling of deep gratitude to all the developers of the methods used in the work of the teachers of this center for the rehabilitation and habilitation of children with mental disorders such as delayed mental or speech development.

These methods have demonstrated a high degree of their consistency in ensuring the quality of the activities of a rehabilitation center for the rehabilitation and habilitation of children with mental disorders such as mental retardation or delayed speech development.

The socio-psychological characteristics of children with autism spectrum disorders are fully subject to the type-species characteristics given in ICD-11. Lack of intelligence is not a fundamental characteristic of children with autism spectrum disorders. However, even in cases of intact intelligence, children of this group, however, do not have a full opportunity to rely on its actual merits to solve the everyday problems of their lives.

Even if the intelligence of children with autism spectrum disorders is preserved, it is aimed at solving problems that are much more interesting for such children (singing, drawing, modeling, collecting, etc.) than building social connections. For these reasons, absolutely all children with autism spectrum disorders require comprehensive social support, which can be received by them as part of the activities of a rehabilitation center.

The work substantiated the methodology for working with practical data obtained during the analysis of qualitative and quantitative practical results of the activities of a rehabilitation center for the rehabilitation and habilitation of children with various disabilities [5].

The collection of experimentally obtained data led to the compilation of appropriate tables, diagrams, and drawings that further demonstrate the dynamics in the accumulation of practical results of the rehabilitation center's activities for the rehabilitation and habilitation of children with various disabilities [6].

Analysis of the data collected during our direct participation in practical activities made it possible to develop proposals for introducing into practice the joint activities of the rehabilitation center and the employment center "My Career" to prepare for employment children with various disabilities who will soon reach adulthood (appendices 1, 2) [7].

These applications also contain the results of surveys, questionnaires, the work of sociometry, events with trips to the employment center "My Career" accompanied by clients of the rehabilitation center, the phasing of the program of the same name formed with our direct participation and the results of its testing in the course of our practice [8].

Already the first sightseeing tour of the rehabilitation center allowed us to properly familiarize ourselves with the structure of this important and necessary public organization, understand its key functions, as well as the main activities of this highly effective social institution.

Joint work with employees of various departments of the rehabilitation center allowed us to get acquainted with the content of the main legislative and regulatory legal acts that determine its activities. These include:

1. On employment in the Russian Federation: Federal Law of April 19, 1991 (as amended on July 1, 2011) [1].
2. On public associations: Federal Law of May 15, 1995 No. 82-FZ [2].
3. On the general principles of organization of legislative (representative) and executive bodies of state power of the constituent entities of the Russian Federation: Federal Law of October 6, 1999 No. 184-FZ [3].
4. On the general principles of organizing local self-government in the Russian Federation: Federal Law of October 6, 2003 No. 131-FZ [4].

During the internship, work was regularly discussed with the director and employees of the rehabilitation center. We were entrusted to participate in the development and effective

implementation of such an effective program as “My Career,” designed to help growing children with disabilities decide on a future profession and become useful members of Russian society.

During the internship, we were entrusted with participating in maintaining the necessary documentation and organizing document flow in the departments of organizations. In particular, we participated in the compilation of tables and diagrams of statistical reporting, which received only partial display in this work due to the limited scope of its planned volume.

We were fortunate to take part in the activities of the rehabilitation center to attract the resources of organizations, public associations and individuals to the implementation of measures for the social protection of citizens, in particular, in supporting the initiative of the rehabilitation center to help older clients - children with disabilities - in more clearly defining their future with support on the part of the employees of the employment center “My Career”.

In the process of this activity, various surveys were compiled and conducted within the rehabilitation center and employment center in order to assess and control the quality of the provision of social services, social security and social assistance measures based on the achievements of modern qualimetry and standardization.

At the same time, a study of the affairs of the client base was also carried out in order to adopt a more accurate calculation program for working with clients of the rehabilitation center and providing them with the necessary assistance. It is necessary to conduct conversations and sociological surveys with clients of the rehabilitation center to improve work.

We were also entrusted with monitoring and facilitating the provision of necessary assistance to clients of the rehabilitation center and direct participation in the development of a program for working with the client base.

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